

Tech-Enhanced Pedagogy: Transforming English Language Instruction

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ABSTRACT

This research explores innovative approaches to teaching English, particularly through the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) tools such as Mentimeter and Padlet. It observes how these tools augment student engagement and learning, specifically within the Critical and Creative Thinking Lab and Pedagogy of English courses in UITTR. This study underscores the significant influence of ICT on improving peer communication and collaboration, confirming the transformative impact of technology on education. The study highlights that the effectiveness of ICT in teaching is largely dependent on teachers' digital competence, with significant variances observed across different regions. Through a qualitative participatory action research methodology, this study involved UITTR students and employed thematic analysis to uncover the challenges and benefits of ICT integration in the classroom. The findings reveal that Mentimeter and Padlet foster interactive and learner-friendly environments, promoting a paradigm shift toward more engaging and learner-centered English language instruction. The study concludes with a call for ongoing professional development to equip educators with the technical, pedagogical, and content knowledge required to harness the full potential of ICT in transforming pedagogical practices

Keywords: Digital divide, e-pedagogy, innovation, professional development, tech transformation.

INTRODUCTION

Innovative practices in the field of English teaching are considered to several extents and represent current trends in language teaching. According to (Buitrago-Florez et al., 2019; Buitrago-Flórez et al., 2021), every teacher can enhance professional skills with the help of values and skills. Similarly, language teaching practices are significant in developing global recognition and cross-cultural perceptions. The evolving strains of contemporary education and global perspectives are crucial in shaping justifiable reforms in the classroom. The need for computer literacy and technological proficiency among language teachers has become dominant in the effective integration of various communication tools and social networks in curriculum development and classroom instruction.

A study conducted in Norway by Krumsvik (2014) emphasized that the pedagogical use of ICT is contingent on teachers' digital competence levels. In Iran, Rezaei and Meshkatian (2017) found that teachers expressed a strong interest in using social networks for instructional purposes and ongoing professional development. In contrast, a survey in Saudi Arabia by Al Khateeb (2017) revealed that despite 60.75% of teachers holding computing credentials, only approximately 25% of English teachers in primary, secondary, and intermediate schools had the digital literacy necessary to employ communicative tools and learning management systems in the classroom. Furthermore, this study revealed that many schoolteachers lacked adequate competence to utilize classroom technologies.

Similarly, Balcikanli (2015) reported from Turkey that teachers with higher academic qualifications demonstrated greater interest and awareness in using social media effectively for student collaboration. The Rezaei and Meshkatian (2017) survey in Iran further revealed that English language teaching (ELT) educators, regardless of gender, age, education and employment status, used social media platforms such as Telegram and WhatsApp to promote blended learning.

In the United States, Chen and Bryer (2012) indicated that most teachers used Facebook for personal connections and LinkedIn for professional networking. However, Fox and Bird (2017), in a mixed-method study in England, identified a gap in the understanding of government teachers regarding the effective use of social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter for professional development. In contrast, Visser et al. (2014) found that technologically proficient teachers in the USA, particularly those adept at Twitter, could join a Twitter-based community of educators, fostering a collaborative culture and enhancing both personal and professional growth. However, Andrei (2017) emphasized that English-language teachers often do not capitalize on available technologies, such as laptops, iPods, digital boards, and internet connections, due to insufficient training in integrating these technologies into classroom settings. These findings underscore the critical role of digital competence and the need for comprehensive

training to ensure that teachers can effectively incorporate technological tools into their pedagogical practices, thus fostering sustainable educational reforms.

In this writing, the author links personal experience and perceptions of the use of several technological tools, such as Mentimeter and Padlet, which are used to evoke activities in the Critical and Creative Thinking Labs and Pedagogy of the English courses of UITTR in the last semester. Therefore, this study focuses on improving student engagement and interaction through the use of ICT tools such as Mentimeter and Padlet. These tools not only foster a more interactive and engaging learning environment but also enable students to collaborate effectively with their peers. Additionally, developing the ability to critically assess and understand the effectiveness of incorporating these ICT tools is essential for transforming English teaching methodologies.

CONTEXT AND INTERVENTION

As a scholar actively involved in research, it is my responsibility to diligently apply and investigate cutting-edge methodologies within the realm of education, specifically in the context of classroom instruction. The aforementioned obligation is in accordance with my academic endeavors within the specific realm of my research focus. During the previous semester, the University Institute of Teacher Training and Research (UITTR) was invited to serve as a facilitator for two different courses. The aforementioned courses that were undertaken by the user include the Critical and Creative Thinking Lab during the seventh semester and the Pedagogies of English during the fifth semester.

The study is grounded in qualitative participatory action research, and its participants are UITTR students enrolled in the English Pedagogy and Critical and Creative Thinking Lab courses at the time of writing. The research cohort consisted of students who were actively engaged in the aforementioned courses at the University Institute of Teacher Training and Research (UITTR). Furthermore, the potential incorporation can also be extended to English-language instructors who have integrated ICT tools into their instructional approaches. Subsequently, students participated in in-depth focus group discussions on their direct experiences with ICT tools and their incorporation into the learning process during the intervention phase. Through thematic analysis of transcribed focus group discussions and interviews, prevalent themes, challenges, and benefits associated with the incorporation of ICT tools into the educational context are identified as part of the qualitative analysis.

In pursuit of my professional responsibilities, I took the initiative to implement an intervention employing two distinct information and communication technologies (ICT) or technological tools, specifically Mentimeter and Padlet. The main objective of this intervention was to determine whether the incorporation of these tools could result in creative and transformative teaching methods in language classrooms. Furthermore, the main objective of this study was to

investigate the potential impact of integrating technology into pedagogical methodologies in the context of English language instruction. The core focus of this intervention revolved around the deliberate and thoughtful process of strategically planning, implementing, and then reflecting on a variety of activities carried out within the classroom setting. The intention behind this approach was to provide a complete understanding of the efficacy and influence of technological tools in improving teaching and learning. The intervention was executed with great attention to detail, adhering closely to a comprehensive diagram that served as a visual representation of the process and methodology used.

The instructional strategy depicted in the figure is ongoing and iterative, beginning with the planning phase. During this preliminary phase, educators design their courses and develop interactive presentations using digital platforms such as Mentimeter or Padlet. In addition, they laboriously compose the guidelines for the forthcoming exercises. The action phase, which occurs after the planning stage, involves implementing organized activities within the classroom setting. In this setting, educators assume the role of guides and facilitators, cultivating an interactive educational environment that motivates student participation through strategically designed digital exercises. The reflection phase marks the end of the cycle during which instructors and students engage in daily self-reflection. At this point, reflections are made on classroom experiences and the efficacy of Mentimeter and Padlet-facilitated activities. The subsequent level of planning is informed by the insights obtained from this introspection, thus establishing a feedback loop that continuously improves the educational experience.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The students who participated in this study used Mentimeter and Padlet to help build their peer-to-peer communication and cooperation skills. Many students noted that both Mentimeter and Padlet are interactive tools that are practical,

relevant, accessible, and learner-friendly programs. Participants at the informal debate in the university noted that both applications were new to them. For instance, one of the students, Aayusha, thought:

After using Mentimeter, I learned a new method to collaborate with friends; even though we are separated by a great distance, we can still make links and talk about problems.

Another student, Shashank, stated that learners can generate learning opportunities and that these two tools can be the best collaboration tools. He continued by saying:

I have never used Mentimeter or Padlet before. When my teacher suggested using them to practice my English, I was inspired to do so. These two applications caught my attention when the digital learning platform was being modified. In addition to typing, email sending and receiving, and resource exploration using various search engines based on the teacher's resources, I also learned many other digital skills. I think these tools can also change the way things are done in the classroom today.

The adoption of current trends in language teaching and learning is related to how students perceive using Padlet and Mentimeter. The students cooperated, coordinated and exchanged ideas with their peers during my observation. As evidence for my interpretation of the study, Parajita reported:

For me, the innovations in the field of language teaching and learning are the mentimeter and the padlet. We do not have to pay anything to use the application, and it is simple to use and manage. It links us to the rest of the world because it allows us to communicate with anyone, anywhere. These programs may encourage us to stay informed about certain topics and limit our time on social networks and WhatsApp.

The comments made by the students were aligned with (Desyarti Safarini, 2019; Gao et al., 2022) as they developed soft skills among the students because they were expected to participate in many tasks through collaboration, cooperation, and communication. As a result of keeping students engaged with tasks and creating learning environments, communication and collaboration have been driving factors in motivating and activating learners to participate in learning contexts in the 21st century.

These responses from the students and my experience indicated that the teaching learning process and the participation of the learners are crucial for pedagogical reformation. As mentioned by (Azizah et al., 2021), the ability of

teachers depends on the planning and the learners to apply. Therefore, learning by doing autonomy of the learner and motivation to learn have been seen. Some of the examples used in the classroom are presented below.

write down three things you learned from the previous sessions

Mentimeter

padlet

Why is lesson plan necessary to teachers? Explain the aspects necessary to plan the lesson.

Vinoda Sethi, 208581057

Lesson plans are necessary for teachers because they provide a clear and concise outline of what to teach, how to teach, and how to assess. They also help teachers to manage their time effectively and ensure that they cover all the necessary content. Lesson plans are also necessary for teachers to differentiate instruction and meet the needs of all learners. Lesson plans are also necessary for teachers to reflect on their practice and make adjustments as needed.

Vinitika Thakur 208521006

Lesson plans are a very important tool for teachers as they help them to organize their thoughts and ideas, and to plan their lessons in a structured and systematic way. Lesson plans also help teachers to identify the key concepts and skills that they want to teach, and to select appropriate resources and activities to support their learning. Lesson plans are also necessary for teachers to track their progress and to make adjustments as needed.

MEETI PAUL SHARDAWAL (208521009)

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Name: Lipakshi JKD 208521008

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padlet

Students' Lab: Poster Designing

Made by Anupam, 190481024

ATTENTION!

Made by Chanchal, 190481024

ATTENTION!

Global Learning: Eyes

The general reflection revealed that technological integration brings about a change in classroom practices, and pedagogical reformation can be observed. According to the views of (Andreasen et al., 2022; Aslam et al., 2021; Campillo et al., 2013) in different situations, teacher preparation can be a tool for reforming pedagogy. Furthermore, they argued that teacher professional development has a connection with changes in the classroom environment where students can practice new skills through technological integration. The connection of new skills, policies, and their implementation can be the landmark to bring changes in classroom practices, especially in English language classrooms, which need to be updated with the values of digital infrastructure; as a result, pedagogical reformation and learning transformation can be observed.

Therefore, English language teachers must acknowledge their professional responsibilities in training students using cutting-edge ICT tools and a variety of online learning platforms to replace traditional memorization and teacher-centered methods for teaching English. Additionally, they must have the technical, pedagogical, and content knowledge and abilities required to teach English using technological tools and applications, especially to reform current pedagogical practices.

FUTURE DIRECTION

Consideration of the educational strategy that incorporated the handheld applications Mentimeter and Padlet, which are examples of information and communication technology (ICT), has produced enlightening results. Peer collaboration and communication abilities improved significantly when students used these tools. As indicated by their feedback, these tools facilitated deeper connections and discussions despite physical distance; in addition to being novel and engaging, they were also practical and learning friendly. Active participation in this context is consistent with the educational paradigm of the 21st century, which places significant importance on communication and collaboration as fundamental motivators in learning environments. Teacher preparation and planning play a crucial role, as evidenced by positive responses from students and the observed increase in student engagement.

Educator methodologies have undergone a discernible transformation since the introduction of technological tools into the classroom. In English-language classrooms, where the incorporation of digital infrastructure is crucial for pedagogical and learning transformation, the introduction of novel policies and competencies can function as turning points in the process of change. In the future, it is critical that English-speaking instructors accept their professional obligation to use different online learning platforms and contemporary ICT tools. By adopting this methodology, an educational shift will occur from conventional rote learning and instructor-centric approaches to English language instruction that is more interactive and student-centered. To reform the prevailing pedagogical practices and improve the overall learning experience, it is imperative that educators acquire and perfect the technical, pedagogical, and content expertise required to utilize these technological tools

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